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MYOFASCIAL PAIN SYNDROME OF THE NECK AND SHOULDER GIRDLE IN PROFESSIONALLY ACTIVE INDIVIDUALS WITH OCCUPATIONAL RISK

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Abstract. Myofascial pain syndrome (MPS) of the neck and shoulder girdle is one of the leading causes of temporary and permanent disability in working-age individuals, significantly affecting their quality of life and professional activity. In this article are presented the results of a study of myofascial pain syndrome (MFPS) of the neck and shoulder girdle in working-age individuals with occupational risk. The clinical and functional characteristics of the syndrome, its etiological and pathogenetic factors, and the impact of occupational stress, length of service, and adherence to treatment and rehabilitation recommendations on recurrence rates are examined. A comparative analysis of indicators in office workers, production workers, and medical personnel was conducted, as well as a comparison with a control group without occupational risk. It has been shown that the use of a professionally oriented diagnostic algorithm and a step-by-step treatment and rehabilitation program helps reduce pain intensity, improve the functional state of the cervical spine, and reduce the frequency of relapses.

Keywords: myofascial pain syndrome, neck, shoulder girdle, office employees, industrial workers, medical staff, occupational risk, functional condition.

Relevance. Chronic pain syndromes of the neck and shoulder girdle are becoming increasingly relevant today [1, 2]. The prevalence of chronic neck pain, in particular myofascial pain syndrome (MPS), among the adult working population ranges from 30 to 50% and is largely associated with occupational risk factors such as prolonged static posture, repetitive movements and physical overload [3–5], which significantly influence the pathogenesis of MPS and therefore do not always allow the cause of the pain syndrome to be identified and the optimal treatment to be selected [6–7].

Despite a significant amount of research, both domestic [8–10] and foreign [12–16], there is still a lack of data on professionally oriented diagnostic algorithms and adapted step-by-step treatment and rehabilitation programmes. The absence of such approaches reduces the effectiveness of standard methods and contributes to the chronicity of pain syndrome in patients from various professional groups, especially those with long-term work experience and non-compliance with rehabilitation recommendations [1, 2, 8, 9].

Thus, the development of professionally oriented diagnostic algorithms and adapted step-by-step programmes for the treatment and medical rehabilitation of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle is a pressing scientific and practical task aimed at reducing the frequency of relapses, improving the functional condition of patients and preserving their ability to work [11].

We were aimed to conduct an epidemiological analysis of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle in various occupational groups and assess the impact of occupational risk factors.

Materials and methods. The research included 180 patients aged 40–60 years (mean age 49.8 ± 0.6 years) with occupational myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle, who were divided into three groups according to their occupation: office employees (n=65), manufacturing employees (n=55), and medical staff (n=60). For each group, information was collected on the length of professional experience, the nature of the workload (static, dynamic, mixed), the frequency and intensity of pain syndrome, as well as medical history data on previous injuries and concomitant diseases. The control group (n=60) consisted of individuals of comparable age and gender who had not been exposed to occupational risk factors for a long period of time.

All participants underwent a comprehensive clinical and neurological examination, including examination of the cervical and shoulder regions, palpation of muscles, identification of trigger points, assessment of range of motion, and testing of reflexes and muscle strength. Functional scales were also used: a visual analogue scale (VAS) to assess pain intensity and the Neck Disability Index (NDI) to determine the degree of functional limitations in the cervical spine.

All data obtained were subjected to statistical processing, including descriptive statistics ($M \pm m$), comparative analysis using Student's t-test and χ^2 for categorical data, as well as correlation analysis to identify the relationship between seniority, workload intensity, compliance with rehabilitation recommendations, and recurrence frequency. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results. When studying occupational risk factors, it was found that the leading factor in the development of pain syndrome among office employees was prolonged sitting and a static working posture, identified in 76.9% of patients, with a recurrence rate of 42%. Frequent minor movements and microtraumas (58.5%) also played a significant role, accompanied by relapses in 35% of cases. Psycho-emotional tension and stress were recorded in 46.2% of those examined and were associated with recurrence in 28% of patients. Workplace ergonomics issues were noted in 38.5% of office workers, with a recurrence rate of 30% (fig.1).

Figure 1. Etiology of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle in office employees (n=65)

For manufacturing employees, heavy lifting and static loads were the most significant factors, identified in 81.8% of patients, with the highest recurrence rate among all groups at 50%. Vibration and frequent movements were found in 72.7% of those examined and were accompanied by recurrence in 47% of cases. Injuries and bruises as an etiological factor were noted in 36.4% of patients, with a recurrence rate of 40%. Poor posture and tense working positions were identified in 45.5% of industrial workers, with recurrences in 38% of cases (fig.2).

Figure 2. Etiology of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle in manufacturing employees (n=55)

Among medical staff, the leading factors were prolonged standing and bending of the torso, which were observed in 80.0% of patients and were accompanied by relapses in 45% of cases. Lifting and moving patients were recorded in half of those examined (50.0%) with a recurrence rate of 40%. Stereotypical movements of the arms and shoulders were identified in 46.7% of healthcare workers and led to relapses in 35% of cases. Emotional and psycho-emotional stress was observed in 41.7% of patients and was associated with recurrence of pain syndrome in 30% (fig.3).

Figure 3. Etiology of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle in medical staff (n=60)

Thus, the highest recurrence rate is observed among manufacturing employees, which is associated with exposure to heavy physical exertion and vibration, while among office employees and medical staff, static postures, frequent movements, and psycho-emotional stress play a leading role.

Next, patients from different professional groups were classified according to gender, age, and prevalence of neck and shoulder pain syndrome (fig.4). An analysis of gender composition showed that females predominated among office employees, accounting for 57% (n=37), while males accounted for 43% (n=28). In the group of manufacturing employees, there was a significant predominance of males (76%, n=42), reflecting the specific nature of this professional activity, while females accounted for 24% (n=13). Females also dominated among medical staff, accounting for 63% (n=38), with males accounting for 37% (n=22).

The age distribution in all occupational groups was comparable. In the office employees group, patients aged 40–49 accounted for 49% (n=32), and those aged 50–60 accounted for 51% (n=33). Among manufacturing employees, the proportion of people aged 40-49 was 45% (n=25), while patients aged 50-60 predominated,

accounting for 55% (n=30). In the medical staff group, the 40-49 age group included 47% (n=28) of those examined, and the 50-60 age group included 53% (n=32).

The prevalence of pain syndrome was high in all groups, but there were certain intergroup differences. The highest incidence of pain syndrome was found among manufacturing employees - 85% (n=47). Among office employees, pain syndrome was observed in 78% of patients (n=51), while among medical staff it was recorded slightly less frequently - in 72% of those examined (n=43).

Figure 4. Comparison of patients from different occupational groups by gender, age and prevalence of pain syndrome

Thus, the data obtained indicate a high prevalence of neck and shoulder girdle pain syndrome in all occupational groups, with the highest frequency among manufacturing employees. The gender and age composition of patients reflects the characteristics of occupational employment and emphasises the significance of occupational risk factors in the development of MFPS.

A comparative analysis of the frequency of myofascial pain syndrome and key clinical and functional indicators in individuals with occupational risk and in the control group revealed that the frequency of the syndrome was significantly higher in the main group of patients, at 78.3%, while in the control group this indicator did not exceed 21.7%. The differences identified were highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating the leading role of occupational factors in the development of MFPS (fig.5).

Figure 5. Comparative characteristics of MFPS frequency and clinical and functional indicators in individuals with occupational risk and the control group

The intensity of pain syndrome on the visual analogue scale (VAS) in individuals with occupational risk was 3.4 times higher than in the control group and amounted to 6.4 ± 0.2 points versus 1.9 ± 0.3 points, respectively ($p < 0.001$). A similar trend was observed in the assessment of functional disorders: the neck dysfunction index (NDI) in the main group reached $34.6 \pm 1.4\%$, while in the control group it was only $9.8 \pm 1.1\%$ ($p < 0.001$).

The presence of active myofascial trigger points was detected in the vast majority of patients in the main group - in 82.2% of cases, which significantly exceeded the corresponding indicator in the control group (26.7%, $p < 0.001$). Restricted mobility of the cervical spine was also significantly more common in individuals with occupational risk factors – in 69.4% of those examined, compared with 18.3% in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

Particular attention should be paid to the analysis of recurrence rates over the course of a year: in patients in the main group, recurrence of MFPS was observed in 57.8% of cases, which was more than four times higher than in the control group (13.3%, $p < 0.001$).

Individuals with occupational risk factors are characterised by a significantly higher incidence of MFPS, more severe pain syndrome, functional disorders, and a high tendency to relapse compared to the control group. This confirms the key role of occupational factors in the pathogenesis and course of myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle and justifies the need to develop specialised, occupation-oriented diagnostic and rehabilitation programmes.

Discussion. The results of the research confirm the leading role of occupational risk factors in the development and chronicity of myofascial pain syndrome (MPS) of the neck and shoulder girdle in persons of working age. The data obtained demonstrate that the prevalence of MFPS in patients with occupational risk (78.3%) significantly exceeds that in the control group (21.7%), which is consistent with the results of foreign and domestic studies indicating a significant contribution of prolonged static and dynamic loads to the development of cervical pain syndromes.

An analysis of aetiological factors showed that the structure of causes of MFPS varies significantly depending on occupational affiliation. For office employees, the leading factors were prolonged sitting and static posture, repetitive small movements, and psycho-emotional stress, leading to chronic muscle strain in the neck and shoulder area, microcirculation disorders, and the formation of active myofascial trigger points.

For manufacturing employees, the leading aetiological factors were heavy lifting, vibration, and repetitive movements, accompanied by a high frequency of relapses. Even with full compliance with treatment and rehabilitation recommendations, this group continued to have a relatively high recurrence rate, which is probably due to the continuing impact of intense occupational stress and the impossibility of completely eliminating it. This confirms the need for longer, multi-stage rehabilitation programmes and close cooperation with occupational health physicians to correct working conditions.

The medical staff of the MFPS developed pain mainly due to prolonged standing, bending of the torso, lifting and moving patients, as well as pronounced psycho-emotional stress. The results obtained emphasise the multifactorial nature of pain syndrome in this category of patients, where mechanical stress is combined with vegetative and emotional components that intensify muscle spasm and contribute to the chronicity of pain.

Conclusion. Myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle in working-age individuals with occupational risk is characterised by high prevalence and is significantly more common than in the control group, confirming the leading role of occupational factors in the development of this pathology. The structure of the etiological factors of MPS has pronounced occupational characteristics: for office employees, the leading factors are prolonged static postures, ergonomic disorders, and psycho-emotional stress; for manufacturing employees, the leading factors are heavy lifting, vibration, and repetitive movements; for medical personnel, the leading factors are prolonged standing, bending, physical overload when working with patients, and emotional strain. The clinical course of MFBS in patients with occupational risk is characterised by greater intensity of pain syndrome, pronounced functional disorders of the cervical spine, a high frequency of active trigger points and significantly more frequent relapses compared to individuals without occupational exposure.

The results obtained justify the need to introduce differentiated, professionally oriented approaches to the diagnosis, treatment and medical rehabilitation of patients

with myofascial pain syndrome of the neck and shoulder girdle in order to prevent chronic pain and maintain working capacity.

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